

A Prospective Study of Evaluate Changes In Macular Thickness After Uncomplicated Cataract Surgery Using OCT in Diabetic Patient

Pinki Kumari¹, Poonam², Gyan Bhaskar³

¹Senior Resident, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Regional Institute of Ophthalmology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 15-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Poonam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cataract surgery is a widely performed procedure that restores vision; however, in diabetic patients, it can lead to complications, such as changes in macular thickness, potentially affecting visual outcomes. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a key tool for monitoring these changes and ensuring timely intervention.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate changes in macular thickness following uncomplicated cataract surgery in diabetic patients using OCT and to assess the influence of the duration of diabetes on these changes.

Methods: 81 diabetic patients receiving uncomplicated cataract surgery were included in the study. Using OCT, macular thickness was assessed prior to surgery as well as one week, one month, and three months afterward. With significance set at $p < 0.05$, statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS.

Results: The study found a significant increase in mean macular thickness from 280.7 μm at baseline to 285.6 μm at 1 week post-surgery and further to 290.3 μm at 1 month post-surgery. By the 3-month follow-up, macular thickness slightly decreased to 287.1 μm but remained elevated compared to baseline ($p < 0.001$). Patients with a longer duration of diabetes exhibited greater increases in macular thickness postoperatively.

Conclusion: Simple cataract surgery in individuals with diabetes results in a temporary but significant increase in macular thickness, particularly in those with a longer duration of diabetes. These findings underscore the need for close postoperative monitoring in diabetic patients to manage potential complications effectively.

Recommendations: To investigate the long-term effects of these macular alterations and to create plans for reducing surgical problems in diabetic patients, more studies with bigger sample numbers and longer follow-up times are advised.

Keywords: Cataract Surgery, Diabetic Macular Edema, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), Macular Thickness, Diabetes Duration.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

One of the most popular surgical procedures done globally is cataract surgery, which has a solid track record of safety and vision restoration effectiveness. However, a number of issues, such as the increased risk of postoperative complications including diabetic macular oedema (DME) and changes in macular thickness, can complicate the results of cataract surgery in individuals with diabetes mellitus. Patients with diabetes frequently have increased retinal permeability and impaired retinal vascular integrity, which might be made worse by the inflammatory reaction that cataract surgery causes. If left untreated, these alterations

may result in postoperative macular thickness, a disease that can impair vision.

Macular thickness may now be measured more accurately and non-invasively thanks to recent developments in (OCT), which also offers important insights into the structural alterations that occur in the retina after surgery. OCT is now a vital tool for diabetes patients' pre- and post-cataract surgery monitoring, helping to identify small changes in the macula that could otherwise go missed. Research has indicated that OCT is capable of identifying macular oedema early on, which is

important for prompt intervention and averting long-term vision impairment [1].

Research on the connection between diabetic individuals' changes in macular thickness and cataract surgery has been continuing. Several studies have shown that, even in the absence of clinically obvious diabetic retinopathy [2], cataract surgery significantly increases macular thickness in diabetic patients. It is believed that the release of inflammatory mediators during surgery is linked to this increase in macular thickness. This can result in the breakdown of the blood-retinal barrier and subsequent fluid collection in the macula [3]. Among the variables that have been demonstrated to affect the degree of macular thickening following surgery are the length of diabetes and the severity of the pre-existing diabetic retinopathy [4].

The clinical importance of postoperative retinal thickening is still up for dispute despite these findings. Although certain research indicates that this thickness is temporary and has no discernible effect on long-term visual acuity, other studies have expressed apprehension on the possibility of chronic macular oedema and its consequences for visual outcomes [5]. With diabetes becoming more commonplace worldwide and the number of diabetic patients having cataract surgery rising, it is critical to comprehend the mechanisms underlying postoperative changes in the macular structure and to develop mitigation techniques. This study aimed to evaluate changes in macular thickness following uncomplicated cataract surgery in diabetic patients using OCT and to assess the influence of the duration of diabetes on these changes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (IGIMS), Patna, a tertiary care hospital with specialized ophthalmology services. The study was conducted over a period of 11 months, from January 2020 to November 2020.

Participants: A total of 81 diabetic patients scheduled for uncomplicated cataract surgery were enrolled in the study. All participants underwent preoperative and postoperative macular thickness assessments using OCT.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 40 years and above.
- Diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.
- Scheduled for uncomplicated cataract surgery.
- Willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Complicated cataract surgeries.
- Patients with systemic diseases other than diabetes that could affect the study outcomes.
- Patients unwilling or unable to comply with follow-up visits.
- Individuals who have had prior eye surgery.
- Existence of additional retinal disorders, such as diabetic retinopathy or age-related macular degeneration.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were enrolled consecutively from those meeting the inclusion criteria. Information bias was reduced by using standardized OCT imaging protocols, and all OCT assessments were performed by the same technician to ensure consistency. Data analysis was conducted by a statistician blinded to the study design to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection: Data were gathered regarding the medical background, demography, and OCT measurements of macular thickness. Preoperative OCT measurements were taken within one week before surgery, and postoperative measurements were taken at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months after surgery.

Procedure: Every patient had gone through uncomplicated cataract surgery performed by experienced surgeons. The procedure involved phacoemulsification and intraocular lens implantation. OCT was used to measure the macular thickness preoperatively and at the specified postoperative intervals.

Statistical Analysis: Software called SPSS 23.0 was used to analyse the data. To summarise the individuals' demographic features, descriptive statistics were employed. The preoperative and postoperative macular thickness measures were compared using paired t-tests. Less than 0.05 was the threshold for statistical significance.

Results

A total of 81 diabetic patients were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 65.4 years (± 8.7 years), with 45 (55.6%) males and 36 (44.4%) females. The average duration of diabetes among the participants was 12.3 years (± 6.5 years). The baseline macular thickness, measured one week before surgery, was found to be 280.7 μm ($\pm 15.3 \mu\text{m}$) on average.

Macular thickness was measured at three postoperative intervals: 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months after surgery. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Changes in Macular Thickness Post-Cataract Surgery (μm)

Time Point	Mean Macular Thickness (μm)	Standard Deviation (μm)	p-value (Compared to Baseline)
Baseline	280.7	15.3	-
1 Week Post-op	285.6	16.1	0.02
1 Month Post-op	290.3	17.2	<0.001
3 Months Post-op	287.1	16.8	<0.001

The mean macular thickness increased significantly one week after surgery, reaching an average of 285.6 μm ($\pm 16.1 \mu\text{m}$). This increase was statistically significant with a p-value of 0.02 compared to the baseline. At one month post-surgery, the mean macular thickness increased further to 290.3 μm ($\pm 17.2 \mu\text{m}$), which was highly significant with a p-value of less than 0.001. By the

third month, the macular thickness slightly decreased to 287.1 μm ($\pm 16.8 \mu\text{m}$), though it remained significantly elevated compared to the baseline ($p < 0.001$).

Subgroup Analysis: A subgroup analysis was conducted to determine if the duration of diabetes had any effect on macular thickness changes.

Table 2: Macular Thickness Changes by Diabetes Duration

Time Point	Group A: Diabetes < 10 years (n = 35)	Group B: Diabetes $\geq$ 10 years (n = 46)	p-value
Baseline	278.4 μm ($\pm 14.5 \mu\text{m}$)	282.5 μm ($\pm 16.1 \mu\text{m}$)	0.15
1 Week Post-op	282.3 μm ($\pm 15.7 \mu\text{m}$)	288.1 μm ($\pm 16.5 \mu\text{m}$)	0.04
1 Month Post-op	287.5 μm ($\pm 16.8 \mu\text{m}$)	292.5 μm ($\pm 17.4 \mu\text{m}$)	0.03
3 Months Post-op	285.2 μm ($\pm 16.2 \mu\text{m}$)	289.5 μm ($\pm 17.1 \mu\text{m}$)	0.07

In patients with diabetes for less than 10 years (Group A), the mean macular thickness increased from 278.4 μm ($\pm 14.5 \mu\text{m}$) at baseline to 287.5 μm ($\pm 16.8 \mu\text{m}$) at 1 month post-op, with the greatest change observed at 1 month. In contrast, patients with a longer duration of (Group B) showed a higher baseline macular thickness and a more significant increase post-surgery, with a peak at 292.5 μm ($\pm 17.4 \mu\text{m}$) at 1 month post-op. The difference in macular thickness changes between the two groups was statistically significant at both 1 week and 1 month post-op ($p < 0.05$).

Complications and Adverse Events: No major complications related to the cataract surgery were reported in the study cohort. Mild postoperative inflammation was observed in 12 patients (14.8%), which was managed with standard anti-inflammatory treatment. No cases of cystoid macular edema (CME) or significant visual acuity loss were reported during the study period.

Discussion

After simple cataract surgery, the study found that diabetes individuals' retinal thickness significantly changed (OCT). On average, macular thickness increased from a baseline of 280.7 μm to 285.6 μm at 1 week post-surgery, and further to 290.3 μm at 1 month post-surgery. Although there was a slight decrease to 287.1 μm by the 3-month follow-up, macular thickness remained elevated compared to baseline levels throughout the study period. These findings suggest that cataract surgery, even when uncomplicated, can cause temporary thickening of the macula in diabetic patients.

The subgroup analysis revealed that patients with a longer duration of diabetes (10 years or more) experienced greater increases in macular thickness post-surgery compared to those with a shorter duration of diabetes. This suggests that the chronicity of diabetes may play a role in the extent of postoperative macular changes. The study found statistically significant differences between the two groups, particularly at 1 week and 1 month post-surgery, suggesting that patients with longer-standing diabetes may require more vigilant postoperative monitoring.

Overall, while the increase in macular thickness was temporary and no cases of (CME) were reported, the study underscores the importance of close follow-up for diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery. The results emphasize the need for clinicians to be aware of potential macular changes in this population, especially in those with a longer history of diabetes.

A research study focused on diabetic patients with varying degrees of retinopathy. Six weeks after surgery, patients with diabetic retinopathy showed significantly higher foveal thicknesses than non-diabetic controls and those without retinal. According to the study, whereas just 4% of patients in the control group experienced macular oedema, 26% of diabetic patients experienced it. The impact of retinopathy on postoperative outcomes in patients with diabetes is highlighted by this finding [6].

After simple phacoemulsification, it was compared the central macular thickness (CMT) of participants

with diabetes to those without the disease. Diabetes is a major risk factor for alterations to the macular structure after surgery, as the study's findings indicate. Diabetic individuals were also more likely to experience increases in CMT following surgery. The study also found a correlation between the length of diabetes and the degree of CMT rise, highlighting the importance of closely monitoring diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery [7].

It was investigated the effects of phacoemulsification surgery on changes in macular thickness in diabetic eyes using OCT. One month after surgery, they observed a considerable increase in central foveal thickness; however, by three months, these alterations had become less pronounced. According to this indicates that although diabetes does raise the risk of macular thickening, the consequences may not last as long [8].

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that simple cataract surgery in individuals with diabetes as measured by (OCT), with the most pronounced changes observed at 1 month post-operatively. The increase in macular thickness was found to be more substantial in patients with a longer duration of diabetes, highlighting the importance of close postoperative monitoring in this population. Although no major complications such as (CME) were observed, the temporary changes in macular thickness suggest a need for careful management of diabetic patients undergoing cataract surgery to prevent potential adverse outcomes. More studies with bigger cohorts and longer follow-up are advised to gain a deeper understanding of how

cataract surgery affects diabetic patients' retinal health in the long run.

References

1. Zhang Y, et al. Optical Coherence Tomography Angiography in Diabetic Retinopathy: A Systematic Review. *Clin Exp Ophthalmol.* 2020;48(4):518-528.
2. Sorkhabi R, et al. Changes in Macular Thickness and Function after Phacoemulsification in Diabetic Patients. *J Ophthalmic Vis Res.* 2019; 14(1):57-64.
3. Wang W, Lo ACY. Diabetic Retinopathy: Pathophysiology and Treatments. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2018;19(6):1816.
4. Panozzo G, Parolini B. Diabetic Macular Edema: Current Management and Future Perspectives. *Curr Diabetes Rev.* 2019;15(6):543-554.
5. Ghasemi Falavarjani K, et al. Macular Thickness Changes after Phacoemulsification in Diabetic Patients Without Retinopathy. *J Curr Ophthalmol.* 2020;32(2):117-122.
6. Jamaiyar A, Kumar S, Kiran N, Mahato RK, Anand M. A prospective study to evaluate changes in macular thickness after uncomplicated cataract surgery using optical coherence tomography in diabetic patients. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2023.
7. Hassanin M, Mohamed MK, Ibrahim MA. Macular thickness changes in diabetic versus non diabetic patients after uncomplicated phacoemulsification. *Al-Azhar Med J.* 2021.
8. Mehta P, Sethia R, Desai V, Patel AC, Shah S. Optical coherence tomography based analysis of changes in macula in diabetes after phacoemulsification surgery. *Indian J Clin Exp Ophthalmol.* 2019.